

Annex D2 – Data on presumptive ESBL-, AmpC- and/or carbapenemase-producing microorganisms and their resistance occurrence (routine and specific monitoring)

Annex to: EUSR on AMR in zoonotic and indicator bacteria from humans, animals and food 2023/2024

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D.2.1. ESBL-, AmpC-, ESBL+AmpC- and CP-phenotypes

Reporting countries determined the susceptibility of *Salmonella* spp. and indicator *E. coli* to selected antimicrobials from different classes (Panel 1), in line with Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2020/1729. Isolates resistant to cefotaxime, ceftazidime and/or meropenem in Panel 1 were further tested with a second panel of beta-lactam antimicrobials, including different cephalosporins and carbapenems (Panel 2). Testing the isolates using Panel 2 facilitated the phenotypic identification of presumptive ESBL-, AmpC- and/or CP-producers. All isolates identified in the specific monitoring of ESBL-/AmpC-/CP-producing *E. coli* and the specific monitoring of CP-producing *E. coli* were susceptibility tested using both Panel 1 and Panel 2.

Also, whole genome sequencing (WGS) has been authorised as an alternative method for phenotypic testing of *Salmonella* spp. and *E. coli* displaying resistance to extended-spectrum cephalosporins or carbapenems. Detailed information is provided in **Appendix A – Materials and methods**.

For this report, the categorisation of isolates displaying extended-spectrum cephalosporin- or carbapenem resistance as presumptive ESBL-, AmpC- or CP-producers was done based on the EUCAST guidelines for detection of resistance mechanisms and specific resistances of clinical and/or epidemiological importance (EUCAST, 2017) and the knowledge of consulted experts.

Five phenotype categories were used: (1) ESBL, (2) AmpC, (3) ESBL + AmpC, (4) CP, and (5) Other. A schematic representation of phenotypic classification based on resistance to beta-lactams included in Panel 2 is provided in Appendix A – Materials and Methods.

D.2.2. ESBL-/AmpC-producers prevalence maps

The prevalence of presumptive ESBL- and/or AmpC-producing *E. coli* in samples from food-producing animals and meat from retail varied markedly between MSs (**Chapter 5**). These variations were also evident when assessing the occurrence of isolates with ESBL- or AmpC phenotypes separately (**Figure 2, Figure 1, Figure and Figure**).

C)

D)

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of the prevalence of presumptive ESBL-producing *E. coli* from (A) broilers in 2024, (B) turkeys in 2024, (C) pigs in 2023 and (D) calves in 2023, in EU MSs, the United Kingdom (Northern Ireland), and non-MSs, 2023–2024. *The designation of Kosovo is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.*

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A)

B)

C)

D)

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of the prevalence of presumptive ESBL-producing *E. coli* from (A) broiler meat in 2024, (B) turkey meat in 2024, (C) pig meat in 2023 and (D) bovine meat in 2023, in EU MSs, the United Kingdom (Northern Ireland), and non-MSs, 2023–2024. *The designation of Kosovo is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence*

A)

B)

C)

D)

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of the prevalence of presumptive AmpC-producing *E. coli* from (A) broilers in 2024, (B) turkeys in 2024, (C) pigs in 2023 and (D) calves in 2023, in EU MSs, the United Kingdom (Northern Ireland), and non-MSs, 2023–2024. *The designation of Kosovo is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.*

C)

D)

Figure 4: Spatial distribution of the prevalence of presumptive AmpC-producing *E. coli* from (A) broiler meat in 2024, (B) turkey meat in 2024, (C) pig meat in 2023 and (D) bovine meat in 2023, in EU MSs, the United Kingdom (Northern Ireland), and non-MSs, 2023–2024. The designation of Kosovo is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence

D.2.3. Key outcome indicator of prevalence of ESBL- and/or AmpC-producing *E. coli* in targeted food-producing animals, 2014-2024

Table 1: Key outcome indicator of prevalence of ESBL- and/or AmpC-producing *E. coli* from targeted food-producing animals, in EU MSs, the United Kingdom (Northern Ireland) and non-EU MSs, 2014-2024.

Country	Period ^(a)									
	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024
Austria	52.1	52.1	60.6	57.0	56.2	52.8	54.0	52.1	53.2	54.0
Belgium	58.2	65.7	71.9	68.1	55.6	56.0	49.0	48.0	47.5	44.8
Bulgaria	58.8	64.3	55.3	51.9	55.7	52.2	37.9	42.1	45.2	40.0
Croatia	33.1	38.8	46.7	48.1	60.6	58.7	60.5	62.8	42.7	35.0
Cyprus	6.8	23.9	19.5	7.5	8.5	7.5	27.0	20.8	11.7	18.5
Czechia	30.8	40.5	42.1	37.6	38.0	34.6	36.0	36.9	40.4	42.2
Denmark	29.1	28.3	24.0	24.0	26.0	25.2	19.0	19.0	14.1	14.1
Estonia	36.8	36.7	35.3	38.2	50.5	48.7	32.6	33.0	19.5	32.7
Finland	4.1	6.3	6.3	6.2	6.2	1.7	4.3	4.7	4.4	4.3
France	39.4	39.6	32.6	26.4	22.1	16.9	10.1	9.9	11.0	11.5
Germany	46.2	46.8	47.4	47.0	48.9	46.9	42.8	43.5	52.6	51.6
Greece	32.8	54.3	59.1	42.4	42.5	47.4	45.7	35.1	45.7	52.0
Hungary	59.0	60.6	67.5	65.8	63.4	53.7	54.3	61.2	53.3	53.9
Iceland	0	3.1	5.3	4.0	6.4	6.5	2.0	1.7	0.7	0.7
Ireland	29.0	42.3	47.6	40.1	45.7	36.1	32.1	30.6	28.3	29.5
Italy		90.0	88.7	82.3	82.4	68.7	65.1	65.3	72.9	71.0
Latvia	48.7	62.3	60.6	43.6	48.8	51.0	48.1	45.1	49.8	44.3
Lithuania	17.9	49.7	67.9	69.3	55.8	51.8	59.2	47.4	44.2	54.5
Luxembourg		52.6	40.9	40.7	52.4	52.2	42.5	41.8	21.3	20.7
Malta	0	0	17.9	45.7	66.9	67.2	52.1	34.2	35.0	52.3
Netherlands	19.8	25.1	23.2	18.4	14.4	12.1	16.4	17.5	21.0	21.1
Norway		10.6	12.8	9.4	12.7	12.4	9.3	9.2	12.2	13.0
Poland	36.7	37.1	43.5	44.5	41.9	34.0	29.7	35.6	41.1	36.1
Portugal	70.1	61.3	56.5	71.4	77.6	65.4	50.8	48.8	59.6	65.7
Romania	55.6	60.8	65.6	66.0	69.4	66.4	65.9	70.7	72.9	66.1
Slovakia	44.3	62.1	66.7	34.9	38.9	72.3	76.7	71.4	74.2	46.1
Slovenia	29.1	71.6	79.0	72.2	75.5	67.5	66.4	51.2	49.4	36.1
Spain	85.3	86.4	85.7	85.7	79.0	73.1	73.0	71.3	70.5	69.8
Sweden	17.8	20.7	22.0	12.3	13.2	12.1	9.2	6.3	1.6	1.6
Switzerland	25.0	30.4	25.1	21.1	19.6	14.3	8.3	7.0	4.1	4.5

(^a) Proportions (in percent) of samples from broilers, turkeys, pigs and cattle weighted by population correction unit that are identified as positive for presumptive ESBL-/AmpC-producing *E. coli* in the framework of the specific monitoring (2020/1729/EU).

D.2.4. ESBL-, AmpC- and CP-encoding genes identified during the specific monitoring of ESBL-, AmpC-, and/or CP-producing *E. coli* and the specific monitoring of CP-producing *E. coli* isolates using whole genome sequencing

In 2023 and 2024, whole genome sequencing (WGS) data on ESBL-/AmpC-/CP-producing *E. coli* were reported by ten countries (Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Finland, Germany, Italy, Sweden, the Netherlands, Norway and the United Kingdom (Northern Ireland)). A range of ESBL-encoding genes was identified across countries and programme codes (**Annex D3 – Table 5, 6, 9 and 10**). The number of isolates carrying the main ESBL-, AmpC-, or CP-encoding genes in *E. coli* across different matrices is shown in **Table 1**.

Overall, **bla_{CTX-M-1}** was the most frequently reported ESBL gene (n=1,213), followed by **bla_{CTX-M-15}** (n=520), and **bla_{SHV-12}** (n=527), the latter being detected predominantly in broilers and broiler meat.

In 2023–2024, nine different plasmid-mediated AmpC-encoding genes were reported (**Annex D3 – Table 7 to 10**). These included **bla_{CFE-1}** (pigs, calves, and their derived meat), **bla_{CMY-24}** (broilers), **bla_{CMY-130}** (broilers), **bla_{CMY-132}** (broilers and broiler meat), **bla_{CMY-101}** (pigs, calves, and their derived meat), **bla_{CMY-102}** (broilers, pigs, and cattle under one year of age), **bla_{CMY-113}** (broilers and turkey meat), **bla_{CMY-155}** (pigs), and **bla_{DHA-1}** (pigs, calves, broilers, turkey meat, and turkeys). In addition, **bla_{CMY-2}** was detected across all matrices.

Two chromosomal mutations were identified: the **C-42T** mutation, which was present in all matrices, and the **T-32A** mutation, which was restricted to pigs.

Overall, the **C-42T mutation** was the most frequently detected AmpC resistance mechanism (n=382), particularly in pigs, calves, and turkeys and their derived meat, followed by **bla_{CMY-2}** (n=219), which predominated in broilers and broiler meat.

For CP-encoding genes, two were reported in 2024 (**bla_{OXA-244}** and **bla_{VIM-1}**) whereas four different genes were reported in 2023 (**bla_{OXA-181}**, **bla_{OXA-48}**, **bla_{NDM-5}** and **bla_{VIM-1}**) (**Annex D3 – Table 9 to 14**). In 2023, the most frequently detected CP gene was **bla_{OXA-181}** (n=31), followed by **bla_{OXA-48}** (n=22), and **bla_{NDM-5}** (n=7).

Table 1: Summary of ESBL-/AmpC-/CP-encoding genes in *E. coli* from targeted food-producing animals and derived meat in retail collected through specific monitoring, in EU MSs, the United Kingdom (Northern Ireland) and non-MSs, 2023-2024.

	Broilers	Turkeys	Pigs	Calves	Broiler meat	Turkey meat	Pig meat	Bovine meat	Total
ESBL-encoding genes									
<i>bla</i> _{CTX-M-1}	140	101	423	302	86	84	42	35	1,213
<i>bla</i> _{CTX-M-15}	18	40	68	274	27	70	6	17	520
<i>bla</i> _{SHV-12}	201	37	36	35	175	33	6	4	527
AmpC-encoding genes									
CT42 mutation	59	30	202	31	15	27	12	6	382
<i>bla</i> _{CMY-2}	92	2	33	6	72	7	6	1	219
CP-encoding genes									
<i>bla</i> _{OXA-181}	-	-	27	4	-	-	-	-	31
<i>bla</i> _{OXA-48}	-	-	21	1	-	-	-	-	22
<i>bla</i> _{NDM-5}	-	-	5	1	-	-	1	-	7

Some countries reported both genotypic and phenotypic data in the framework of routine monitoring of indicator commensal *E. coli*, as well as in the specific monitoring of ESBL-/AmpC-/CP-producing *E. coli* and CP-producing *E. coli*. These results are presented in **Annex D3 – Table 15 and 16** and are also available in a separate Excel file, which provides the correspondence between phenotypic resistance, based on MIC values, and resistance phenotypes predicted from genotypic data.